

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EARLY CHILDHOOD EXPERIENCES AND
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN
CALABAR SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA**

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between early childhood experiences and academic performance of secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Ex-post facto research design was used. A sample size of two hundred and twenty-six (226) Junior Secondary School Three (JS 3) students was randomly selected from a population of 1,501 students of all the eight public secondary schools, representing 15 percent of the students in each of the schools in Calabar South Local Government Area. Two instruments titled “Early Childhood Experiences Questionnaire” (ECEQ) and “English Language Achievement Test” (ELAT) were used for data collection. Cronbach Alpha (∞) method was used to determine the internal consistency of the “Early Childhood Experiences Questionnaire” (ECEQ) while the reliability coefficient was 0.83. Guttman split-half reliability estimate was used to determine the reliability coefficient for the English Language Achievement Test (ELAT) and 0.75 was obtained. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the research hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. Results obtained from the study showed that 62% of variation in students' academic achievement in English Language was due to deprived play and deprived play has significant relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area; 23% of variation in students' academic achievement in English Language was

due to living environment deprivation and there is also a significant relationship between it and academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in the target area. It was recommended that parents/guardians should allow their kids to interact with other kids, and the school management should provide variety of play materials in schools in addition to provision of adequate space for play.

Introduction

Education is a process of methodical training and instruction intended to transmit knowledge and acquire skills, potentials, and abilities that will enable an individual to effectively contribute to the growth and development of his society and nation. Education is an indispensable tool in the building of any nation. It encompasses a person's entire growth—physical, social, moral, intellectual, and mental (Osakwe, 2006). Children education intended for ages three to six is known as pre-primary education. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) in the National Policy on Education, sees pre-primary education as the education given in an educational institution to children aged 3-5 years plus prior to their entering the primary school. In other words, early education is a unique type of instruction given to kids in a facility before they start primary school.

In an effort to increase the societal utility of the outcomes of our educational system, the government has made a concerted effort to improve the quality of education at all levels. Early childhood education will therefore, provide children with the essential physical, psychomotor, affective, cognitive, and social potentials that are fundamental to human life and will play a very important role in their academic performance in primary school and beyond. This is the main issue that this study aims to examine.

Learning, according to Osakwe (2006) is a natural process that involves pursuing meaningful objectives and deriving meaning from experience and information that has been filtered via the individual perceptions, ideas, and. For this reason, learning begins as soon as a child is born to help him adjust to the new system. Prior to learning, to sit, walk, talk, and behave like the people around him, the child learns to feed, hear, see, and react to stimuli. A child's behavior may fluctuate from day to day as he attempts to balance his reliance from infancy and his dependence from youth. In an effort to learn more, he goes deeper and exposes himself to the world around him. The drive for curiosity is innate in every child and can be developed to yield greater results by given him early education. This early experience exposes the child to all fields which make him more apt to learn in the primary level as the confidence in his

learning capabilities, which he acquired from the nursery school is lifted to the primary school.

Most parents believe they are providing their kids with everything they need and yet despite this, they are still falling short of their potentials. Maybe they do not mind that they are sacrificing their emotional stability for their children's financial stability. The situation is worse in certain homes where both parents work. Children in urban areas must wait until a holiday to see their parents, as raising a higher standard of living is the primary issue that needs to be resolved by parents. This way of living and these reckless behaviors cannot be used to impart knowledge to the next generation. In this sense, we are providing economic security at the expense of security related to emotions, culture, behavior, education, etc. In order to prevent waste and stagnation in the education of the deprived children, deficiencies in the family, school, and social environments as the primary cause of educational deprivation should be checked and modified right away (Singh, 2017).

The majority of parents have some limitations regarding the space, equipment variety, educational resources, and experiences they can provide for their kids. In situations where mothers are the only source of support or income for the family, many parents are overburdened with their own worries that they will not be able to provide their children the direction they require as they deal with difficulties and frustrations. In a crowded apartment without playmates or supplies necessary for play, children may be left in the care of inexperienced and unwell adults. This can lead to neglect and deprivation, which can have detrimental long-term impacts on the child's life. However, healthy growth and adjustment take place if the formative years are marked by exposure to a wide range of learning activities and social connections, expert education, and astute guidance. According to Abbas, Ansari, and Rizvi (2015), early childhood education provides children with a comprehensive experience in democratic life that fosters collaboration and minimizes competitiveness. This experience in groups, expands the values of the family.

The majority of senior secondary school students in Nigeria have significant emotional strains in addition to the difficulties of managing their academic work. These strains are often brought on by long commutes, unfavorable school conditions, uninspired professors, etc. These would undoubtedly be unfavorable to academic achievement. The impact of domestic violence on children is one detrimental component of family life. Depending on the interparental connection, children may witness domestic violence or become victims of it themselves, which can cause serious trauma. Domestic violence is defined as a pattern of aggressive and coercive

behaviors used by adults or adolescents against their intimate partners. These behaviors might include physical, sexual, psychological, and economic coercion.

The results of the 2015/2016 May/June exam were announced by Eguridu (2016), the Head of National Office (HNO) of WAEC. Of the 1,605,248 candidates who registered for the exam, 1,593,442—864,096 males and 729,346 females—took the test. He claims that of the 1,593,442 candidates who took the test, 1,498,069 or 94.01 percent have had all of their results released, while 95,373 or 5.99 percent have some of their subjects still pending because of minor errors. Additionally, he reported that 616,370 candidates or 38.68 percent of the total, earned credits in five courses or more, including mathematics and English language. In the May/June 2014 WASSCE, 529,425 out of the 1,746,125 candidates (30.32 percent) obtained a minimum grade of C6 while in May/June 2013, 639,334 out of the 1,689,188 candidates representing 38.30 percent obtained a minimum grade of C6 in Mathematics. In a report according to Daily Trust Newspaper, 21st August 2014, it was stated that the percentage pass of students in WASSCE Mathematics in the year 2012 was 38.81 percent while that of 2011, 2010 and 2009 are 38.15 percent, 41.51 percent and 45.33 percent, respectively.

The researchers speculate that the pupils' early experiences may have contributed to their failure. A child's early experiences will provide them access to critical physical, psychomotor, affective, cognitive, and social potentials that are essential to human life and will have a significant impact on how well they perform academically in elementary school and beyond. This study looked into how certain early experiences—like being denied of play, being abused as a child, being socially excluded, not receiving an education, and not receiving affection—affect children's academic achievement in the English language.

Statement of the Problem

Every parent raises their child differently in Nigeria these days. Every parent has high hopes for their children, but due to their degree of exposure, the majority of them are unable to fulfill their aspirations. This really affects the way they bring up their children knowing the fact that it is solely the responsibility of the parent to train up a child. The rearing practices which the child is exposed to influences his values, norms, and belief even in later life. The contents of the knowledge which the child is exposed to early in life are bedrock to later education and life. Even the scripture gives the injunction, “train up a child in the way he should go and when he is old, he will not depart from it.”

The alarming rate of failure in our secondary schools is highly embarrassing. The issue of poor academic performance of students in Calabar South Local Government Area in English Language has been of much concern to all stakeholders such that it has led to the widely acclaimed fallen standard of education in Cross River State at large. The State government on realization of the problem of the poor academic performance of students, embarked on school quality improvement measures which included the building of infrastructures, employment of more teachers, etc. It was, however, observed that even with all these interventions, performance of students in West African Secondary School Examinations (WASSCE) in the State is still poor.

There is need, therefore, to investigate the number of issues that can contribute to the poor performance in English Language. Hence, this question: Can poor performance in English Language be as a result of early childhood experiences since the same teacher that produce the best students are the same that produce the students that fail. It is based on the foregoing therefore, that this study aimed at investigating the relationship between early childhood experience on students' academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. Specifically, the study investigated the relationship between deprived play, living environment, deprived education, deprived affection and students' academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine the relationship between early childhood experiences and academic performance of secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area. Specifically, this study intended to:

1. Find out if deprived play has any relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.
2. Determine whether living environment deprivation has relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used as guide for the study:

1. How does deprived play relate with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area?
2. To what extent does living environment deprivation relate with academic

performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area?

Statement of hypotheses

The following hypotheses served as guide to this study:

1. Deprived play does not have significant relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant relationship between living environment deprivation and academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Method

The study adopted the ex-post facto research design. The population of the study comprised all the 1,501 Junior Secondary School Three (JS III) students in the eight public schools in the Area, comprising 647 boys and 854 girls in Calabar South Local Government Area. The sample of the study was made up of 226 Junior Secondary School Three students randomly selected and representing 15 percent of the students in each of the schools.

Data were collected using the “Early Childhood Experiences Questionnaire” (ECEQ) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT). The ECEQ comprised two sections - A and B; Section A of the instrument sought information about the personal data of the subjects while Section B comprised 24-items which sought information about early childhood experiences like deprived play, living environment deprivation, deprived education and deprived affection, with six items measuring each of them. Each response on the questionnaire was given a degree of scores which ranges from one to four; from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. The achievement test comprised 20 questions in English Language test items for JSS 3 students to measure their academic performance in the subject. The validity of the instruments was determined by two Psychologists and one Measurement and Evaluation experts. Items in the instruments were scrutinized independently by the experts. Their comments and suggestions were applied appropriately to improve the quality of the instruments before using it for data collection. ECEQ and ELAT were administered to 30 JSS3 students randomly selected from two secondary school in the Calabar Municipality that were not part of the sample but shared similar characteristics with those in Calabar South. The data collected for the ECEQ were scored and analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability method which gave reliability coefficient of 0.83. The reliability of the ELAT was established using Guttman split-half reliability

estimate which gave a coefficient of 0.68 and Spearman Brown prophecy coefficient of 0.75.

Data collection was done in the sampled schools. The researchers first visited the sampled schools to familiarize with the school authority and explained the purpose of the study and secondly, the school teachers helped the researchers to administer the instruments. The researchers first administered the questionnaire to the respondents and was immediately followed by the English Language achievement test.

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The mean value of 2.50 was used as a benchmark for decision, while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One

How does deprived play relate with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on how deprived play relates to students' academic achievement in English Language

N = 226				
S/N	Item Statement	Mean (X)	SD	Dec.
1	My parents do permit me to go out for relaxation exercises.	2.22	0.79	D
2	My parents do not permit me to run and play with my friends.	3.10	0.90	A
3	My parents rarely took me to recreational centers to play with other children	3.17	0.81	A
4	My parents don't permit me to play at whatever point they take me out.	2.16	0.69	D
5	My parents do permit me to play with other neighbour's kids.	3.22	0.83	A

Dec = decision, A = agreed, D = disagreed

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of respondents on how deprived play relates to students' academic achievement in English Language. The result obtained show that items 2, 3 and 5 had mean ratings of 3.10, 3.17 and 3.22 with standard deviations of 0.90, 0.81, and 0.83, respectively. These mean values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 which implies "agreed". This means the following responses on how deprived play relates to students' academic achievement in English Language are agreed. These include my parents do not permit me to run and play with

my friends’, ‘my parents rarely took me to recreational centers to play with other children’, ‘my parents do permit me to play with other neighbour's kids’. However, ‘my parents do permit me to go out for relaxation exercises’, and ‘my parents do not permit me to play at whatever point they take me out’ are disagreed because their mean values are less than 2.50 which implies “disagreed”.

Hypothesis One

Deprived play does not have significant relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) Analysis of the Relationship between deprived play and students' academic achievement in English Language

Variables	N	R	R ²	P-Value	Dec
Deprived play	226				
Students' academic achievement in English Language	226	0.79	0.62	0.02	S

N = Number of students, Pearson Product Moment Correlation = R, R² = Coefficient of determination, P-value = Probability value, Dec. = Decision

Table 2 shows that the correlation between deprived play and students' academic achievement in English Language was 0.79. This shows that there is a strong and positive correlation between deprived play and students' academic achievement in English Language. The coefficient of determination 0.62 (known as the predictive value) means that 62% of variation in students' academic achievement in English Language was due to deprived play. A probability value of 0.02 was obtained and since it is less than 0.05 set as level of significance ($P < 0.05$), this means that the result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that deprived play does not have significant relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area is rejected. Inference drawn therefore is that deprived play has significant relationship with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Research Question Two

To what extent does living environment deprivation relate with academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on how living environment deprivation relates to students' academic achievement in English Language

N = 226				
S/N	Item Statement	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Dec
6	The noise in my area disturbs me a lot.	3.00	0.68	A
7	My parents did not assist me in lesson at home when I was young	2.19	0.73	D
8	I have a comfortable room.	2.22	0.75	D
9	I do not have good toilet facilities where I live.	3.05	0.72	A
10	There is good source of water where I live.	3.06	0.72	A

Dec = decision, A = agreed, D = disagreed

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviations of respondents on how living environment deprivation relate to students' academic achievement in English Language. The result obtained shows that items 6, 9 and 10 had mean ratings of 3.00, 3.05 and 3.06 with standard deviations of 0.68, 0.72 and 0.72, respectively. These mean values are above the benchmark value of 2.50 which implies “agreed”. This means the following responses on how living environment deprivation relate to students' academic achievement in English Language are “agreed”. These include; ‘the noise in my area disturbs me a lot’, ‘I do not have good toilet facilities where I live’, and ‘there is good source of water where I live’. However, ‘my parents did not assist me in lesson at home when I was young’ and ‘I have a comfortable room’ was “disagreed”, this is because its means value is below the benchmark value of 2.50.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between living environment deprivation and academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) Analysis of the Relationship between living environment deprivation and students' academic achievement in English Language

Variables	N	R	R ²	P-Value	Dec
Living environment deprivation	226	0.48	0.23	0.04	S
Students' academic achievement in English Language	226				

N = Number of students, Pearson Product Moment Correlation = R, R² = Coefficient of determination, P-value = Probability value, Dec. = Decision

Table 4 shows that the correlation between living environment deprivation and students' academic achievement in English Language was 0.48. This shows that there is a strong and positive correlation between living environment deprivation and students' academic achievement in English Language. The coefficient of determination 0.23 means that 23% of variation in students' academic achievement in English Language was due to living environment deprivation and a probability value of 0.04 was obtained. Since the probability value of 0.04 is less than 0.05 set as level of significance ($P < 0.05$), this means that the result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between living environment deprivation and academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area is rejected. It is, therefore, inferred that there is a significant relationship between living environment deprivation and academic performance in English Language among secondary school students in Calabar South Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

Deprived Play and Students Academic Achievement in English Language

The result obtained from table 1 showed how deprived play relates to students' academic achievement in English Language to include: my parents do not permit me to run and play with my friends, my parents rarely took me to recreational centers to play with other children, my parents do permit me to play with other neighbour's kids. The result in table two showed that 62% of variation in students' academic achievement in English Language was due to deprived play. Also, there is significant relationship between deprived play and students' academic achievement in English Language in Calabar South Local Government Area. This result concurred with Brockman, Jago and Fox (2011) who stated that children's primary motive for engaging in physically active play was for social and enjoyment reasons, to prevent boredom and because they were aware of the physical and emotional benefits of being active. They also valued the freedom from adult control and the unstructured nature of physically active play. The finding is also in line with the findings of the study by Kamene (2015) who investigated the effect of play on school children academic performance in Yatta Sub-County, Machakos County, Kenya and found that there was also greater improvement in the mean score between the pre-test and post-test when children were exposed to types of play. When children were exposed to teacher initiated and guided play, they tended to record the highest improvement in their mean score. Role play and group play also significantly enhanced school children academic performance.

The finding is in accordance with that of the study by Obondo (2011) which was to determine the impact of play on academic performance of early childhood education in Mbita West Zone, Suba District, Kenya and found that play helps the children perform well in class. Play makes the children like the school environment; children who play do not find difficulties in solving problems and play improves children's performance in the later years. The study revealed that the most common games mentioned were football, net ball, hide and seek, running, jumping, riding bicycles and driving toy cars, swinging parallel play, followed by collaborative play and negotiating play.

Living Environment Deprivation and Students Academic Achievement in English Language

The result obtained from table 3 showed how living environment deprivation relates to students' academic achievement in English Language to include: the noise in my area disturbs me a lot, I do not have good toilet facilities where I live, there is good source of water where I live. The result in table four showed that 23% of variation in students' academic achievement in English Language was due to accessibility of resource materials. And there is significant relationship between living environment deprivation and students' academic achievement in English Language in Calabar South Local Government Area. This result is in agreement with findings of Ajila and Olutola (2007) who stated that the home environment or family background of students affects their academic performance, and they further revealed that home environment sharpens the child's initial view of learning. Parents' beliefs, expectations and attitudes about education also have a profound early impact on students' conceptions of the place of education in their lives. The finding is in accordance with that of Dosunmu and Sowunmi (2013) who investigated the impact of deprivations in childhood on the academic performance of secondary school students in ghetto areas in Lagos, Nigeria and discovered that there is a significant difference between the extent of deprivation experienced in the formative years between ghetto public secondary school students and private secondary school students, and there is a significant difference between the extent of deprivations experienced in the formative years when examined among secondary school students whose fathers are of different educational status.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Parents/guardians should allow their kids to interact with other kids and the school management should provide variety of play materials in schools in addition to provision of adequate space for play.

2. Parents/guardians should provide a conducive environment to their children.
3. Parents/guardians should endeavour to take proper care of their children academic need.
4. Awareness campaigns and programmes should be created by the school authority especially during the PTA meetings to educate parents and caregivers on the need to show proper care and affections to their wards.

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